

EIC User Group Newsletter

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Prepared by

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NEWS

- The [4th Yellow Report Workshop](#) at LBL-Berkeley (California) was held **online on 19-21 November**. It was the **last** in a series of workshops dedicated to the **preparation** of the EICUG **Yellow Report** (YR). The agenda was roughly split in **three parts**. The **first** one focussed on the **physics** case and on the **key results** obtained by the Physics Working Groups, with summaries of various **detector requirements** depending on the considered class of reactions (exclusive, inclusive, etc..). The **second** part focussed on identifying the **key features** of the **detector** that could match these requirements. Ample time was reserved for discussion on updates of the **Detector Matrix** and on possible **tensions** between requirements and constraints on the actual capabilities of the device. The **last** part of the agenda was left to illustrate the status and developments of the **YR draft** (see bullet below), and to address other issues: discussing the case for a **second interaction region** and detector complementarity; reviewing the status and plans of the received **Expressions of Interest** (a complete list of received EoI's is publicly available at <https://indico.bnl.gov/event/8552/> - please click on "received input" on the sidebar); thinking how to organise an **archive of data and/or software** used in the simulations, etc.. All material can be found at the [Indico agenda](#) of the workshop.
- During the workshop, there was a **competition** to select the best design for the YR cover. The work of **Yulia Furletova** was selected from the community by far the **best YR cover design** out of [11 submitted](#). Congratulations to Yulia and to all other competitors.

- During the workshop, the **YR draft** (updated to Nov. 19th) was made available through a link on the workshop home page. The **revised timeline** for next steps in the editing process was also presented. After the workshop and until Dec. 20th, the draft will be edited/updated/revised by the Steering Committee and by all the Conveners of the Physics and Detector Working Groups. **From Dec. 21st until Jan. 6th**, the draft will be opened to **input from the EICUG community**. Requested input is of two types: specific comments (wording, grammar, content, disagreement), or general comments across sections (consistency, logic, duplication, missing topics). Directions on how to submit input will be circulated at proper time. From Jan. 6th to Jan. 12th, the draft will be edited to fold the received input in. The main time constraint is **Jan. 12th**, when the YR draft will have to be posted as pre-brief material for the **CD-1 review** by DOE. In the second half of January, an independent team of external readers will read, review, and comment the draft. This team is being formed by the Steering Committee; the final list of appointed names will be announced when ready. Finally, during February the draft will be edited for folding in the input from external readers. The goal is to release the **final version** of the Yellow Report by the **end of February**, including submission to the **arXiv**.
- During the workshop, the **authorship policy** for the YR draft was also discussed. The authors team will consist of an **inclusive list** of all EICUG members who **actively contributed** to the YR studies and its writing process. This list will appear once at beginning of the YR draft to highlight that the document is a EICUG community effort. During the editing process, the Physics and Detector (sub-)working groups co-Conveners will collect necessary information by distributing a standard web-based form through their (sub-)group mailing list. In addition to the author team, a **separate list** will be highlighted which includes the names of the Physics, Detector, and Software (sub-)working groups **co-Conveners**, as well as of the **Steering Committee**. Finally, an **acknowledgments** section will be appended to the YR draft, where credit to **funding agencies** can be added, if needed.

NEWS from the CONFERENCE & TALKS COMMITTEE

- Please, consult the list of **open EICUG talks** at <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/open> . For a list of **previous EICUG talks** see <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/previous> (often including also a link to the presentation). If you wish to recommend a candidate, including yourself, or if in general you wish to suggest new speakers (including yourself) to be considered for future invitations, please contact the Conference & Talks Committee at eicug-talks@eicug.org . Here, you can find also the general [talks guidelines](#) .

NEWS from the INSTITUTIONAL BOARD

- The **EICUG** currently stands at **1200 members**, from **245 institutions** in **33 countries**. The **theory members** are approximately **25%**, **experimentalists** **61%**, **experts in accelerators** **13%**, and a **1%** is shared between **Computer scientists** and **Support**.

This is the **bar chart** of the **245 Institutions** of the EIC IB, divided by **country**.

- We would like to celebrate the **1200th member** of the EICUG: **Shukui Zhang** (Jefferson Lab). Congratulations!
- Since previous Newsletter, **four more institutions** joined the EICUG:
 - * University of Hawai'i at Manoa (US)
 - * Universidad Autonoma de Sinaloa (Mexico)
 - * California Polytechnique State University, San Luis Obispo (US)
 - * Morehead State University (US)

NEWS from the ELECTION & NOMINATION COMMITTEE

- By next Dec. 31st, **two members** at large of the **Steering Committee** (SC) are rotating off:

- John Arrington (LBL, USA)
- Marco Radici (INFN Pavia, Italy)

and also the **Institutional Board (IB) Chair and vice-Chair**:

- Christine Aidala (Univ. of Michigan, USA)
- Andrea Bressan (INFN Trieste, Italy)

Only Andrea Bressan completed his first term, all others cannot be re-elected.

- The Election & Nomination Committee has been seeking input from the EICUG community about nominations for candidates for the above positions, by the deadline of Dec. 7th. Based on these nominations, the Committee will prepare **two slates of candidates**, one for the SC and one for the IB, after checking availability of nominees and considering balance by geography, gender, and expertise. The Committee will open the elections when the slates will be ready.
- The **two most-voted** candidates in the SC list will take the two vacant positions. The **most voted** in the IB list will act as the **IB Chair**, while the **second-highest** will act as the **IB vice-Chair**. Members of the SC can be any member of the EIC Users Group, while the IB Chair and vice-Chair need to be an institutional representative. The elected IB Chair will become ex-officio member of the SC. For the elections to be **valid**, it is a requirement that **at least 50% of the IB** representatives vote.

RECENT WORKSHOPS/MEETINGS of INTEREST

See also <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/previous> (includes also links to some presentations)

Those events labeled by were held with on-line only format.

[5th International Conference on Particle Physics and Astrophysics \(ICCPA 2020\)](#), Moscow (Russia), 5-9 October 2020

[EIC Workshop - Promoting Colaboration on the Electron-Ion Collider](#), Cockcroft Inst. (UK), 7-9 October 2020

[LXX International Conference NUCLEUS-2020](#), Saint Petersburg (Russia), 11-17 October 2020

[APS DNP Fall meeting](#), 29 October - 1 November 2020

[Opportunities with Heavy Flavor at the EIC](#), CFNS (Stonybrook-US), 4-6 November 2020

[The 17th International Workshop on Hadron Structure and Spectroscopy](#) (IWHSS 2020), Trieste (Italy), 16-18 November 2020

[Jets for 3D imaging at the EIC](#), Riverside (CA-US), 17-18 November 2020

[4th Yellow Report Workshop at LBL](#), Berkeley (CA-US), 19-21 November 2020

[Fast Machine Learning for Science Workshop](#), Southern Methodist Univ. (US), 30 November - 3 December 2020

[Perceiving the Emergence of Hadron Mass through AMBER@CERN](#), CERN, Geneve (Switzerland), 30 November - 4 December 2020

[Resummation, Evolution, Factorization \(REF 2020\)](#), Univ. Edinburgh (Scotland), 7-11 December 2020

UPCOMING WORKSHOPS/MEETINGS of INTEREST

See also <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/upcoming> and <http://cnr2.kent.edu/~manley/BRAGmeetings.html> (the latter is temporarily not updated due to the current “stay at home” order)

The events labeled by will be held only on-line. If joined by “?”, it means that a decision is not yet taken.

[EIC Physics in the Snowmass process](#), CFNS (Stonybrook-US), 11-15 January 2021

[3rd Proton Mass Workshop: Origin and Perspectives](#), Argonne Nat. Lab. (US), 14-16 January 2021

[Forward Physics and QCD with LHC, EIC and cosmic rays](#), 20-23 January 2021

[New Physics Phenomena - Hadronic Contributions to New Physics Searches](#), Crete (Greece), 21-27 March 2021 ?

[DIS 2021 - XXVIII Int. Workshop on DIS and Related Subjects](#), Stony Brook (NY-US), 12-16 April 2021

[Open questions in photon-induced interactions - From relativistic nuclear collisions to the EIC](#), CFNS (Stonybrook-US), 26-29 April 2021 ?

[QCD Evolution 2021 Workshop](#), UCLA (US), 10-14 May 2021

[RHIC Science programs informative toward the EIC in the coming years](#), CFNS (Stonybrook-US), 24-27 May 2021 ?

[Origin of the Visible Universe: Unraveling the Proton Mass \(INT-20-77W\)](#), INT Seattle (WA - US), 4 - 8 May 2020 **Postponed**

[Transversity 2020](#), Pavia (Italy), 25-29 May 2020 **Postponed** to May 2021

[2nd workshop on Jets for 3D imaging at the EIC](#), CFNS (Stonybrook-US), 16-18 June 2021

[Light-Cone 2020](#) (LC2020), Jeju (Korea) 5-10 July 2021 as **LC2021**

[The XIVth Quark Confinement and the Hadron Spectrum Conference](#), Stavanger (Norway), 2-7 August 2021

[Lepton-Photon 2021](#), Manchester (UK), 9-14 August 2021

[22nd International Conference on Particles and Nuclei \(PANIC2020\)](#),
Lisbon (Portugal), 30 August - 3 September 2021

[Experimental applications of Artificial Intelligence for the EIC \(AI4EIC-Ex\)](#), CFNS (Stonybrook-US), 6-10 September 2021

Quarks and Nucleon Physics (QNP 2021), Bonn (Germany), 20-24
September 2021

[Workshop on the QCD Structure of the Nucleon \(QCD-N2021\)](#), Univ.
Alcalà (Spain), 4-8 October 2021

[24th International Spin Symposium SPIN2020](#), Matsue (Japan), 11-15
October 2021

[Baryon 2020](#), Sevilla (Spain), 19-22 October 2021 as **Baryon 2021**

[Tomography of light nuclei at an EIC](#), ECT*-Trento (Italy), 25-29 October
2021

[8th International Conference on High Energy Physics in the LHC era](#),
Valparaiso (Chile), 3-8 January 2022